

Checklist

Measurement and data planning for machine learning in assembly

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1. Foreword

Data quality plays an important role in fully utilizing the potential of artificial intelligence or machine learning in industry, especially in assembly. The following checklist was developed as part of a cooperation between the Lab for Measurement Technology and the Chair of Assembly Systems within the framework of the ERDF project „Messtechnisch gestützte Montage“ and the follow-up project „iTecPro – Erforschung und Entwicklung von innovativen Prozessen und Technologien für die Produktion der Zukunft“. Future development is carried out in the project "NFDI4Ing – the National Research Data Infrastructure for Engineering Sciences", funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – 442146713. It is intended to support industrial users, especially in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), in recording high-quality data to minimize the effort required for analysis and increase the 'results' significance.

This checklist was initially published in German by Schnur et al. on Zenodo and has now been translated into English [1].

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1.1. Objectives, limitations, and focus of the checklist

This checklist is intended to support the planning of a project to use machine learning on an existing assembly line (Brownfield). Therefore, the focus is not on acquiring a new plant or data planning for prototypes in product development. Nevertheless, the checklist can also provide orientation for these use cases. It pursues the approach of recording valid data as precisely as possible through the contribution of expert knowledge and making it available and accessible. Due to the immense diversity of available machine learning methods, data analysis is only dealt with at a basic level within the scope of this document. The primary target groups of this checklist are manufacturing SMEs and large companies.

1.2. Structure of the checklist

A short paragraph introduces the topic at the beginning of each chapter, followed by checkpoints to be ticked off. Two types of checkpoints are distinguished: **necessary** and **best practice checkpoints**.

Necessary checkpoint

Best practice checkpoint

The necessary checkpoints are those that must be implemented for the successful processing of the following chapters. Best practice checkpoints are not necessary for the processing of the sections. Still, they have proven to be very helpful in further optimization.

Furthermore, the checklist contains helpful tips (recommendations for action) and hints (things you should pay attention to) to support you in your work.

Tip

Note

2. Preparation and project planning

Already during the preparation, there are several aspects to consider in creating a good starting point for your project. Although the following points seem trivial, experience shows that they are often neglected in practice. Even if a large amount of production data usually already exists in the company, good preparation is essential to advance your project successfully. Within the scope of this checklist, only points of project management that are critical for data quality are mentioned. You should still consider other vital points, such as budget planning or risk analysis.

Thoroughly read and understood the checklist

Before you start processing, you should have read the checklist entirely and understood the individual work steps.

Objectives and nature of the project defined

Think carefully, ideally in a cross-departmental meeting with process experts, about your project's goals. Do you, for example, want to monitor the condition of products, processes, or plants? Do you want to record data specifically at only one plant, or do you want to record data across stations or plants? Do you want to optimize the processes with the most downtime or reject them?

Note

Machine learning is built on statistical analysis and can only provide meaningful results if the information you are looking for is contained in the data.

Experts identified

Try to identify the respective experts for your products, processes, and plants and convince them of your project. Expert knowledge is precious for planning, evaluating, and interpreting your data.

Note

Often, (specific) process knowledge can only be found among individuals in the company and is thus difficult to access, which can enormously hinder data evaluation and analysis.

Archive checked for similar projects

Before you start planning, check whether similar projects have already been conducted in your company (or your sector). If so, look at the available project documentation and try to incorporate what you have learned from those projects into the current project.

Overview of possible products, processes, and plants created

Create an overview of the products, (assembly) processes, and plants that come into question for your analysis.

Effort realistically estimated

Most of the effort in analyzing data in machine learning is in the preparation of the data (approx. 80%) and only 20% in the actual analysis. This applies especially the communication with the experts who are only available sporadically and are not directly included in the project can delay the schedule.

Focus of observation defined

Try to keep your focus of observation as small as possible. Bundle your resources and do not get lost in evaluating data from too large and complex plants. Instead, start small, e.g., with a single (critical) process, and expand your analysis later.

Schedule created

By when do you want to complete the project? Create a schedule with milestones that you want to achieve.

Work packages derived and divided

Derive work packages and divide them among your staff.

Coordination and responsibilities clarified

One person must take responsibility and coordinate, drive, and ensure that the project schedule adheres.

Employees educated and commitment obtained

Often this point is essential because interests within the company overlap. If employees do not understand your project, it will most likely fail, especially in production, where a high number of units and, thus, low downtime plays the overriding role. Here, adjustments or solutions to problems during downtime are not always documented due to time constraints. Try to identify and integrate” “project opponents“ and ensure their willingness to support the project. A workshop, for example, can promote acceptance among employees.

Specifications created

Create a specification sheet. What are the requirements to be met? What statements should be made based on the recorded data (e.g., system condition, damage detection, etc.)?

3. Measurement and data planning

After the initial preparations are completed, the measurement and data planning can begin. First, it is essential to record or build up basic process knowledge and identify existing norms or standards. Your data is usually not exclusive to one department, so a uniform and understandable data structure with all necessary metadata is essential.

Note

Measurement and data planning is an iterative process and may (or must, if necessary) be adjusted.

Tip

Make sure that **knowledge/information is always available** in your project! Use existing structures and procedures in your company for data storage and documentation. If you need to set up a new structure, follow the FAIR data principles; see <https://www.fairsharing.org/>. FAIR stands for **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable, and **R**eusable. Note that „FAIR“ data is not the same as „open“ data. Findability or accessibility can also be exclusive to your company or individual departments.

3.1. Build up and use process knowledge

Already existing features identified

Which features are already recorded in your plant or process, and for whom (which department) are they relevant? E.g., Which characteristics are essential for the assembly, quality, or automation department?

Quality requirements identified

Talk to your quality assurance and/or your customers and document important measurement/test variables.

Cause-effect diagram created

Create a cause-effect diagram, also called an Ishikawa diagram. This will help you to identify the causes of problems or influencing factors.

Interference variables identified and their influence determined

To obtain a robust machine learning model, determining interfering variables and considering their range of values or influence is enormously significant, as the learning models are usually unable to extrapolate. Interference variables can be, for example, temperature, humidity, manufacturer tolerances, and employees (at manual workplaces). The cause-effect diagram and the process expert can support you in determining the interference variables.

Influence of interference variables minimized

According to the point, „Interference variables identified and their influence determined“ minimizing the influence of interference variables makes sense. Check to what extent this is possible in your project. For example, limiting to a single product type variant helps eliminating product-specific influences.

The use of additional sensors considered

If, for example, you have identified relevant variables or characteristic values based on your cause-effect diagram or according to your process 'experts' recommendation, consider installing additional sensors. Additional sensors do not necessarily have to be physical; virtual sensors can also be used to calculate values from measured variables.

Tip

If you decide to use additional sensor technology and are unsure which sensors you need, try more accurate or higher-quality sensors first. Many sensor manufacturers will also help you select sensors and provide them for test measurements. Alternatively, some companies also offer sensors for rent.

Overview of sensors created

Create an overview of the sensors used with all relevant information. You can use the following points as a guide:

- Sensor name
- Sensor type
- IP address
- Manufacturer
- Measured variable
- Unit
- Sampling rate
- Bandwidth
- Resolution
- Output signal (communication, voltage)

3.1.1. Use norms and standards

Internal standards researched

Many companies have already developed their internal standards and guidelines for data recording. You should check these first and use them if they are suitable.

External standards and norms researched

Check whether there are already established standards or norms for data recording in your sector or the industry in general.

Note

- If norms or standards already exist for your field, it is strongly recommended to use them or build on them. For example, the International Organization for Standardization (**ISO**) and the European Committee for Standardization (**CEN** or **CENELEC**) should be considered.
- For the automotive industry, the Association of Standardization of Automation and Measuring Systems (**ASAM**) offers standards in various disciplines, such as measuring systems, data management, simulation, and many others.

3.2. Structure of the data

Data format selected

Consult with your process and data analysis experts and select a suitable file format uniformly. Ideally, the file format should be non-proprietary and already established. It should also be as easy as possible to add metadata.

Data structure selected

Consider how to structure your data in a meaningful way. Neither countless small files nor one large file with all the data is recommended here. Consider the compatibility of the data structure with already existing/used databases within your company.

Unique naming of the data selected

By naming your data clearly and uniquely, you increase the manageability of your data immensely.

Descriptive naming of the data selected

By giving your data a descriptive name (e.g., Date_Time_Product_Station_Sensor), you also increase the manageability of your data. The possible level of detail for a descriptive naming depends strongly on the complexity of your system and your project because too long file names can lead to problems in the analysis.

Automatic annotation of the data ensured

Manual or subsequent labeling poses a potential risk of incorrect metadata, especially with high volumes.

A clear relationship between the data to the individual products established

To enable later evaluation across stations, it is necessary to assign the data to the assembled products, e.g., via the serial number (unique ID).

Metadata to be recorded selected

Select relevant metadata, such as machine and sensor configurations.

Comprehensible description of the metadata selected

Each measurement must be described clearly, thoroughly, and understandably. With the help of the metadata or documentation, a project outsider should be able to answer the W-questions (Who, What, How, Where, When, and Why?).

Format of time stamps defined and documented

- Separator (point or comma)
- Format
- Specify the date and time together or separately.
E.g., date (DD.MM.YYYY); time (hh:mm:ss)
- Unique time reference (UTC, local time, other?)

Reference systems adapted and documented

Adapt zero points, references, and coordinate systems to each other and document it in the metadata.

Label reference runs and test measurements

If the data you are recording includes reference runs, test measurements, reference patterns, or similar measurements that deviate from the regular operation, clearly label them as such or save them separately.

Storage of threshold values

Save the threshold values of individual processes in the metadata as well.

Clear definition of measured values and critical figures provided

Especially in the case of key figures, different formulas are often used for calculation (e.g., Overall Equipment Effectiveness - OEE). Define and document the formulas used.

Non-digital knowledge or data digitized

Often helpful information can be found in non-digital knowledge and data, e.g., shift books, maintenance books, etc. Document this information by digitizing it. In the simplest case, use a photo or scan and save it with the (meta-)data.

Tip

A uniform structure and a suitable data format make the data more accessible and easier to process. Some best practices for data formats have developed from various experiences. For example, for larger amounts of data, a binary format such as **HDF5** [2] or similar (**TDMS** for **NI LabVIEW** [3]) is suitable for larger amounts of data because of its simple structuring and use. On the other hand, formats that are open (non-proprietary) and more readable for humans are more suitable for smaller amounts of data. These include, for example, the **CSV format** [4], which is particularly useful for manually entered data. The **JSON format** [5] is suitable as a human- and machine-readable exchange format for automated systems (e.g., databases).

3.3. Data storage

Existing data collection systems integrated

Try to integrate the captured data of existing data capture systems into your data repository as well.

Note

Experience shows that the interfaces from the sensor to the server are not implemented as quickly as desired/thought. Plan additional time here if necessary.

Storage requirements estimated

Estimate the required storage and calculate a safety margin.

Suitable platform for data storage selected

Select a suitable platform for data storage, considering company policies and anticipated storage space requirements, if applicable. Examples would be Hard drives, servers, or a cloud.

Data backup selected

To prevent data loss, you should store your data with a suitable strategy (e.g., the 3-2-1 backup rule in combination with RAID systems) [6].

3.4. Integrate manually collected data

Tip

Using standards and drop-down lists enables the machine readability of manually entered data.

Note

Manually collected data often contain relevant information for interpreting occurrences in data and are, therefore, crucial for analysis.

Human influence reduced

Reduce human influence to a minimum, e.g., by:

- Uniform wording based on a glossary
- Drop-down lists
- Error categories
- Standard error codes

Digital shift books introduced

The introduction of digital shift books increases the accessibility of the information they contain [7]. Especially in case of discrepancies in the data, the shift book can provide valuable information.

Documentation of all state changes ensured

All types of interventions, changes, and adaptations to plants, processes, and equipment must be documented.

Comment section implemented if required

Especially in the case of unforeseeable complications, a section for additional text, although not directly machine-readable, can be helpful for the error description.

Images integrated as an additional data source

Pictures, especially in the case of mechanical defects, can also be helpful for your analyses.

Allows mapping of manual data to automated data

Enable the assignment of manual data to automated data, e.g., via time stamp, product ID, or similar. Note that metadata also plays a significant role here.

4. Data acquisition

After the *measurement and data planning* has been done, the first data can be recorded. A sharp separation between measurement and data planning, and data recording is not possible, as one will typically have to make adjustments after evaluating the first data.

4.1. First test measurement and data quality check

Test measurements carried out

Conduct a first test measurement under real conditions. The measurement should not be too extensive but contain several measurements from all sensors.

Tip

It makes sense to record time-continuous data at the beginning or later at regular intervals (“curve data”). E.g., after a number X of produced parts, time-continuous data are recorded of Y produced parts.

Data structure checked

Check that the data has been stored in the desired structure (measured values and metadata). Forward the recorded data to the data analysts and ensure the data structure is understandable, complete, and workable.

Proper function of the sensors checked

Check, ideally with the process experts, whether the sensors are functioning correctly and delivering plausible values. For example, you can plot the corresponding data points and check the measurement. Suppose sensors do not record any or unexpectedly constant measured values (e.g., 0). In that case, this may indicate an error in data acquisition. Also, check whether you can detect quantization steps in your measurement signals and, if necessary, replace the sensor with a sensor with a higher resolution or better analog-to-digital converter (ADC).

Synchronization of the data acquisition systems ensured

Check that your data acquisition systems run sufficiently synchronized with each other. A maximum deviation of 10% of the cycle time is a reasonable basis for assembly processes. This step is essential for sensor fusion.

Assignment of data to processes and products ensured

Ensure that your data can be clearly assigned to the corresponding products and processes (e.g., via the product ID). Only then an analysis of multiple plants is possible.

Data quality evaluated

Try to evaluate the quality of your data (and increase it if necessary), e.g., by using the six dimensions of data quality dimensions [8]:

- Accuracy
- Completeness
- Consistency
- Timeliness
- Validity
- Uniqueness

4.2. Long-term data recording

Inspection intervals set

Set regular intervals for checking data quality. In the beginning, this should be more frequent to be able to intervene early in case of malfunction.

Proper function of the sensors checked

Check that all sensors are still working correctly and providing plausible values.

Statistical significance tested

Unfortunately, there is no valid answer to the question, „How much data do I need for machine learning?”. In principle, it is not the specific number of recorded measurements that matters but rather that the data represent the spectrum of regularly occurring disturbance variables (such as temperature fluctuations, manufacturer tolerances, etc.). Therefore, check the statistical significance of your disturbance variables, e.g., with hypothesis tests [9].

First data analysis carried out

Carry out an initial data analysis (cf. chapter Data evaluation and modeling) to identify relevant sensors or features early and interpret their behavior. Remember that unfavorably sensor types or mounting positions might have been selected.

5. Data check and data cleansing

Even with optimal planning and the best possible execution of your measurements, mistakes and errors will happen. Therefore, you need to check and clean the data after recording. These errors do not necessarily have to be human but can also come from your data acquisition system. This is a normal process, especially in iterative approaches, and should not unsettle you.

Data structure checked again

Check whether the recorded data still is in the desired structure and correct any deviations.

Missing information added

If necessary, add missing information, such as target values or metadata.

Data combined

Suppose you have several individual data records, e.g., from several stations. In that case, you can combine them by using the product ID or the time stamp.

Blind spots identified

Areas where data is not (cannot) be recorded are called blind spots. The gaps in the data caused by blind spots should be filled, if possible, by empirical knowledge and physical correlations.

Data cleansed of invalid measurements

Remove measurements from your dataset where the measured value (unintentionally) has always taken the same value or zero.

References and zero points adjusted

If you use different references or zero points for measurement data or time stamps, merge them to ensure the same reference system.

Reference runs and test measurements separated

If the data you recorded also contains reference runs, test measurements, or similar measurements that deviate from the regular operation, sort them out. You should not simply delete them, as information about the condition of your system can be obtained over time.

Outliers removed from the evaluation

Outliers are measured values that deviate recognizably and justifiably from the rest of the measured values and their variance [10]. Remove outliers from your evaluation if they are not physically plausible or significantly influence the distribution of your data.

Units checked and unified

Incomplete, missing, or wrong units are a considerable risk in data analysis. In the example of length measurement, it makes a big difference whether you measure in meters or inches. Convert all measured values of a measurand into the selected standard unit.

Distribution shift balanced

Check whether your data distribution is drifting and, if necessary, compensate for this drift if it is not the desired information.

Data cleansing documented

Document the steps taken, with additional comments if necessary.

6. Data evaluation and modeling

Machine learning cannot and should not be seen as omnipotent regarding data interpretation. Instead, it should be seen as a compass that guides you toward the right path to interpret your data. Before you build a machine learning model, you should first build a basic understanding of the data.

6.1. Data understanding

Suitable time scale selected for visualization

Use a suitable time scale for the visualization of your data. For example, the ambient temperature in production halls rarely changes abruptly within a few minutes; drifts occur over the day or the week. Reasonable observation periods could be, for example, by shift, day, or week.

Signal curves plotted in the time series diagram

Take a look at the signal curves of your measurements. Do not focus exclusively on one signal here but plot several measurements (of the same or different sensors) in a diagram. Try to get a feeling for your data this way.

Quasi-static signals plotted

The quasi-static signal can also provide information about your process, e.g., it can help you identify drift effects. In the context of this article, a quasi-static signal is a signal created by stringing together a selected data point in a measurement over a series of measurements.

Histograms plotted

Histograms also provide valuable insights into your data. It is often easier to identify outliers by displaying the histogram of a process. For example, the histogram can also recognize process-specific or supplier changes.

Boxplot diagram plotted

By clearly displaying several positions and dispersion measurements of a process in a single box, it is easy to compare identical processes [11].

Principal component analysis performed

A Principal Component Analysis (PCA) in combination with significant target variables can be used to identify the biggest influences on the data. By coloring according to the target variable (or disturbance variables such as ambient temperature, layers, or batches), clusters can be identified.

Error patterns examined and interpreted

Investigate and interpret error patterns in individual systems or stations and their effect on the overall system.

Note

- Only compare like with like.
- When comparing with two or more diagrams: Label axes correctly, scale them the same, and use the same units.

6.2. Selection of machine learning algorithms

State-of-the-art reviewed

Research the current state of the art by searching the web or literature, attending training courses or specialist conferences, if necessary.

Available computing power checked

A criterion that should not be underestimated when selecting machine learning algorithms and especially when optimizing their parameters is the necessary computing power. The lower your available computing power, the longer your calculation will take and the longer your system will be blocked if you do not switch to resource-saving algorithms.

Note

Depending on the selected algorithm and scope of the data, training a machine learning model, including validation, can quickly go from several hours over several days to several weeks. You should take this into account and test simple models or algorithms first.

Learning problem defined

In principle, a distinction is made in the industrial context between classification problems (e.g., damaged/undamaged or damage A/B/C) and regression problems (e.g., service life 0-100%) as well as anomaly detection, i.e., detection of new states caused by changed boundary conditions or disturbance variables. Depending on the selected learning problem, different algorithms are relevant.

Tip

If you have **little** or **no experience with** machine learning, consider outsourcing the data analysis. This does not necessarily have to be a company. You can also approach research institutes or universities for research projects (as an active or associated partner). You will often find motivated researchers with expertise but limited access to „real-world data“. In this way, both industry and research can benefit.

Note

Given the large number of existing machine learning algorithms, no algorithm can be applied universally per se and is equally well suited to all learning problems.
Be aware that you will undergo an iterative process with a changing combination of different algorithms.

Suitable and realistic validation scenario selected

Perhaps the most important and often underestimated point in machine learning is selecting a suitable validation scenario. Creating a machine learning model that classifies your data with 100% accuracy (classification problem) or predicts the desired target variable (regression problem) is easy in principle. However, this model is most likely unreliable and suffers from overfitting, i.e., in the simplest case, it learns the test data patterns by heart. By consciously dividing your data into training, validation, and test data, you can check how well your model performs on the „unknown“ data. (Group-based) cross-validation is an established method to avoid overfitting. Suppose you also vary the free parameters of the ML model (so-called hyperparameters). In that case, you need additional test data which are not included in the modeling to check for overfitting with the hyperparameters. Be sure to test the actual transferability of your algorithm with one (or more) realistic validation scenarios. This is the only way to assess your 'model's robustness against disturbance variables.

Tip

A good introduction to the validation of machine learning algorithms is provided by Maleki et al. in their review paper „Machine Learning Algorithm Validation - From Essentials to Advanced Applications and Implications for Regulatory Certification and Deployment“ [12].

Feature extraction algorithms selected

Often the individual measurement points of measurement (raw data) are of little significance, so it is essential to extract relevant features from them. These can be, for example, mean values and slopes over defined intervals (linear fit), frequencies from the frequency spectrum, or statistical values (standard deviation, kurtosis). Feature extraction usually reduces the dimensionality of the data considerably, which on the one hand, simplifies the calculation of suitable models and, on the other hand, reduces the tendency to overfitting.

Tip

The free ML toolbox DAV³E (Data Analysis and Verification/Visualization/Validation Environment) with a graphical user interface developed at the Lab for Measurement Technology can support you in analyzing your data [13]. The toolbox combines selected algorithms for feature extraction, feature selection, and classification or regression.

DAV³E can be downloaded from <https://github.com/lmtUds/day3e-beta>.

A script-based version of the toolbox can be found at: <https://github.com/ZeMA-gGmbH/LMT-ML-Toolbox>.

Feature selection algorithms selected

Especially in complex systems with a high number of sensors, a high number of features can result. To save resources (computing power and time) and to prevent overfitting, the number of features can be reduced by selecting the most relevant ones. This can also be done by simple algorithms such as correlation analysis or more complex algorithms (or a combination of both).

Algorithms for classification or regression selected

Select algorithms for classification or regression according to your learning problem. First, use simple approaches, e.g., for classification, a Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) in combination with a k-nearest neighbor classifier or, for regression, a Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR). These approaches not only have low demands on computing power but can also be well visualized so that one gets a first impression of the model quality. Higher-level methods, such as artificial neural networks, are often black-box methods with results that can hardly be interpreted. An overview of the most common algorithms can be found in [14].

Additional anomaly detection applied

Due to the often-high amount of „good“ data and few „bad“ data in production, it is worthwhile to implement an additional anomaly detection. This detects when the distribution of your process or station changes above a previously defined level and then issues a message/alert. Should this shift occur due to an error, the corresponding measurements can be annotated and fed into a machine-learning model.

Note

Artificial neural networks and machine learning are linked in the public mind and are associated with each other. If you are considering using neural networks in an industrial context, be aware of the following points:

- **Neural networks are a black box**
You cannot be sure that the neural network produces the correct result for the wrong reasons (overfitting, correlation, and causality).
- **High data volume required**
A large amount of data is required to achieve reliable results, which includes all possible interferences (compare training in image recognition with typically >14,000,000 annotated training images). This is often not the case in the industry.
- **The selection of a suitable type or architecture is not trivial**
Many different types of neural networks exist, where you are practically not restricted in the respective architecture.
- **High computing power or dedicated hardware required**
Although neural networks can be parallelized very well, this often requires dedicated hardware (servers, cloud computing).

6.3. Modeling

- Performance of the machine learning algorithms compared**
Compare the performance of your chosen algorithms in the different validation scenarios. For classification, this is primarily the percentage of correctly classified validation or test data, and for regression, the mean square error for validation or test data.
- Suitable learning algorithms selected**
Select suitable algorithms based on the performance. The algorithms do not have to be the same for all sensors and can also differ from sensor to sensor.
- Model uploaded for application**
Once your model has been trained, you can upload it to the intended application location (this does not have to be on the station but can also be on a server or the cloud) for use.
- Model controlled**
After a reasonable time, use the additional data from production to check whether your machine learning model continues to deliver the desired and, above all, plausible results. If this is not the case, you may need to record more data containing the cross-influence of the disturbance variable (which led to the error) or revise your ML model.

6.4. Model application

Regular validation of the model scheduled

You should regularly check whether your model still provides meaningful and plausible data.

Regular re-training of the model scheduled

You should re-train your model at regular intervals. This way, you can also include newer data in your model, compensate for drift effects, and at best, increase the robustness of your model.

Hardware and software changes documented

Document any changes to the state of your process or system. Consider version control (e.g., via GitLab) of your software and machine learning model to be able to view previous models. Be aware that if the hardware is changed significantly, the ML model may need to be fundamentally re-trained, as the data patterns and distribution before and after the modification may no longer match.

7. Project completion

In contrast to the application and regular optimization of your machine learning model, your project must be completed at a specific time. To benefit in future machine learning projects from your accumulated experience of this project, it is essential to provide your approach, findings, and all documentation clearly and thoroughly.

Analysis results compared with the initial objective of the analysis

Compare your initial objective with the actual analysis results and document the deviations.

Lessons learned formulated

In every project, mistakes or things that could have been improved inevitably arise. So not only do you learn from the project, but you should also formulate your lessons learned for future employees and projects.

Final presentation created

Create a short final presentation in which you clearly state your project objectives, approach, achievements, and limitations. This will enable your colleagues to grasp your project and build on it quickly.

Final report drafted

Write a final report; it should be as comprehensive as necessary but at the same time as short as possible.

All documents centrally stored

Check whether all necessary documents, programs, and, if applicable, data have been stored centrally and can be easily found.

8. Conclusion

After studying this checklist, a first insight quickly emerges: data planning and -evaluation are time-consuming. One of the reasons for this is that both never lead to a perfect result. Iterations and constant reprocessing are necessary to maintain continuous improvement. It also follows that this checklist is not a one-off guide to be worked through but instead serves to improve measurement and data planning constantly.

For this purpose, own knowledge and experiences from projects can and should be included in the processing because the checklist does not represent a stand-alone sample solution but rather an additional help.

9. List of abbreviations, glossary, and bibliography

9.1. List of abbreviations

ADC	Analog to digital converter
Approx.	circa
ASAM	Association of Standardization of Automation and Measuring Systems
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
cf.	compare
CSV	Comma-separated values
e.g.	for example
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format Version 5
ID	Identifier
IP	Internet Protocol
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LDA	Linear discriminant analysis
NI	National Instruments
OEE	Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE)
PCA	Principal Component Analysis (PCA)
PLSR	Partial Least Squares Regression
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
TDMS	Technical Data Management Streaming
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time

9.2. Glossary

Anomaly detection	Detection of irregularities.
Backup	Backup of data on another medium to prevent loss of data.
Best practice	Already established procedure/method/process.
Black Box	In systems theory, a black box refers to a system whose inner structure or functioning is unknown. The observer only sees what goes into the black box (input) and what comes out (output).
Brownfield	Already existing production or plant.
Drift	The slow change of the measured or output variable over time.
Drop-down lists	Fold-out list with predefined elements.
Feature	Extracted variables, including sensor readings, statistical values (e.g., mean values), key figures (e.g., OEE), or similar.
GitLab	Version management web application for software projects.
LabVIEW	Graphical programming system from National Instruments.
Lessons Learned	Lessons learned.
Neural networks	Algorithms inspired by the human brain (artificial neurons).
Overfitting	Overfitting of a model on the data.
Plot, plotting	Graphical representation.
Quasi-static signal	Signal results from juxtaposing a selected data point over several measurement series.
RAID system	Redundant arrangement of independent hard disks for backing up data.
Validation	Method to see if the model reliably fulfills its practical purpose.

9.3. Bibliography

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Note

The literature listed serves as an aid to provide readers with a low-threshold introduction to the relevant topics. Readability and accessibility had priority over scientific depth.